

THE ROLE OF BIOMARKERS IN THE DIAGNOSIS OF UNDIFFERENTIATED CONNECTIVE TISSUE DYSPLASIA

A.V. Muratkhodzhaeva¹, A.M. Zokirova²

Tashkent State Medical University^{1,2}

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17118042>

Abstract. *Undifferentiated connective tissue dysplasia represents a pressing challenge for modern clinical practice, attracting the attention of physicians, geneticists, and specialists from different medical fields. Timely and accurate diagnosis of this condition is crucial, yet remains problematic due to the absence of universal laboratory criteria. Numerous diagnostic methods and biochemical tests have been suggested, but most of them demonstrate only relative reliability and cannot be considered as absolute markers. In this context, the search for informative biomarkers—such as amino acids, collagen derivatives, or glycosaminoglycans—has become an essential direction of current research.*

Keywords: *connective tissue dysplasia, proline, hydroxyproline, biomarker, glycosaminoglycan, research methods.*

Introduction. Disorders in connective tissue metabolism during the intrauterine and extrauterine phases result in connective tissue dysplasia, a genetically determined syndrome. Impaired production of type II collagen is a hallmark of connective tissue dysplasia, which is brought on by structural anomalies in extracellular matrix constituents and gradual morphofunctional alterations in different organ systems. Since connective tissue is found in the human body in the form of dense connective tissue (bone and cartilage), hematopoietic tissue, and blood cells in addition to connective tissue itself, it is in fact responsible for trophic, metabolic, and immune functions in addition to preserving the shape of organs.

Current research indicates that almost 80% of people have connective tissue dysplasia (CTD), a prevalent disorder, according to the SmartClinic website. 85.4% of youth had individual symptoms of connective tissue dysmorphogenesis, according to a therapeutic publication. However, many people may live with CTD without being aware of it, and not all cases are clinically noticeable. The involvement of connective tissue dysplasia in the emergence of diseases in different human organs and systems has recently drawn the attention of researchers and medical professionals. This issue is significant since lesions are common and there is a high likelihood that other kinds of diseases may develop [1].

In the form of distinct morphofunctional diseases of internal organs and their functions, connective tissue dysplasia is a condition that causes homeostasis issues at various levels of the body. This disease is becoming more common every day [2]. Biomarkers can be used to diagnose this issue. Following the breakdown of type 1 or type 2 collagen and its fragments, peptides were produced in the blood serum. Furthermore, biomarkers can also be derived from metalloproteinases. [3]. Bone fractures can be identified by the presence of pentosidine and homocysteine in urine and plasma. It is feasible to anticipate bone fractures with the use of N-telopeptides. [4-5].

These days, it's critical to identify diagnostic indicators in kids with connective tissue dysplasia. The presence of ether-bound and free fatty acids in blood plasma is currently recognized as a supporting diagnostic analysis. It has been discovered that children with hereditary ischemic heart disease have unique characteristics in the structural redistribution of certain fatty acids. [4]

There is a magnesium shortage in several bodily parts, including hair, red blood cells, and oral fluid, in connective tissue dysplasia. It is reasonable to believe that low magnesium ion concentrations have pathogenetic importance in these situations. Collagen fibers, elastin fibers, and hyaluronic acid polysaccharide strands are all more likely to break down when magnesium levels are low. The mechanical characteristics of arteries and venous vessels may alter as a result of hypomagnesaemia. [7–11].

Since collagen is a protein, we are aware that it is made up of amino acids. Thus, we can diagnose or assess the level of collagen degradation based on changes in the levels of hydroxyproline, lysylpyridinoline, deoxypyridinoline, galactosyllysine, hydroxylysine, carboxyterminal and aminoterminal telopeptides, type I collagen degradation products in blood serum, and pyrylinx-D in daily urine.

One of the primary amino acids found in collagen is oxiprolin. In connective tissue dysplasia, it may be seen as an indicator of collagen catabolism. After collagen breaks down, the liver metabolizes about 75–80% of hydroxyproline-containing peptides, while the kidneys eliminate 20–25% of peptides in the urine. Low molecular weight peptides contain the majority of the hydroxyproline found in urine. Roughly 7–9% is high. There is one percent free hydroxyproline. A violation of collagen production is indicated by a rise in the concentration of free hydroxyproline and a fall in the amount of non-free hydroxyproline [12].

The skeletal system contains the majority of collagen. Compared to soft tissue, bone tissue regenerates more quickly. As a result, numerous researchers are working to create techniques for identifying bone collagen. Following collagen's post-translational modification, hydroxylysine and amino acids combine to generate hydroxylysine glycoside. Although it is released from bone tissue, it remains inert and is entirely eliminated in urine. In the tissue of the skin, lysine reacts with glucose and galactose. The primary building block of bone collagen is galactosyllysine, which is created when galactose and hydroxylysine combine. Consequently, this element may function as a particular indicator of the deterioration of bone collagen. The quantity of hydroxylysine glycosides may be accurately determined by chromatography-mass spectrometry [14].

The structure of fibrils is stabilized by molecular cross-links. These amino acids, which include lysylpyridinoline, deoxypyridinoline, and hydroxypyridinoline, include pyridine. The release of pyridine derivatives from bone tissue is a sign that mature collagen is breaking down. Pyridinoline is found in cartilage collagen, whereas deoxypyridinoline is found in bone collagen. Consuming collagen with meal has no effect on their excretion. Chromatography is used to identify pyridinoline cross-links in hydrolyzed urine [14].

One particular bone protein that binds calcium is called osteocalcin. Osteoblasts synthesize it, and it attaches itself to extracellular microcrystals. The amount of osteocalcin, total amino-terminal propeptide of type I procollagen, and alkaline phosphatase activity in blood serum can all be used to measure the rate of bone production. Only a little portion of freshly produced osteocalcin makes its way into the circulation. As a result, the enzyme immunoassay technique created by the Swiss business Roche can be used to quantify it. [11]

Finding the amounts of specific amino acids, hydroxyproline, and glycosaminoglycans in daily urine as well as lysine, proline, and hydroxyproline in blood serum are the most informative ways to diagnose connective tissue dysplasia in a lab setting.

Materials and methods. The study was conducted among 135 children at the 4th City Children's Clinical Hospital. The children were aged 5 to 16 years, and 105 of them had phenotypic and visceral signs of connective tissue dysplasia, while 30 children without signs of connective tissue dysplasia were selected as a comparison group. In the morning, on an empty stomach, samples were collected from all children for laboratory diagnosis and sent to the laboratory. The method of choice was the determination of the concentration of lysine, proline and hydroxyproline in blood serum.

The normal concentration of lysine is 82.7–239.5 $\mu\text{mol/L}$; proline is 97 to 368 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, and the normal concentration of hydroxyproline in children aged 2–15 years is 8.6–45.2 $\mu\text{mol/L}$.

Research results.

Table 1.

Amino acid name (normal value)	Main group (No. 105)	Comparison group (No. 30)
Lysine (82.7–239.5 $\mu\text{mol/L}$)	238.2	198.3
Proline (97–368 $\mu\text{mol/mL}$)	359.5	272.4
Hydroxyproline (8.6–45.2 $\mu\text{mol/L}$)	46.3	24.6

The results (Table 1) of the analysis show that patients with signs of connective tissue dysplasia had higher values than patients in the comparison group.

Conclusions. Patients with connective tissue dysplasia had high levels. The control group had normal levels. This means that lysine, proline, and hydroxyproline can be used as laboratory indicators and laboratory methods for studying connective tissue dysplasia. This method can be used to confirm this problem. This method is more accessible to everyone. However, the accuracy of the current method is not very high. To make an accurate diagnosis, doctors need to take a comprehensive approach to patients. They need to consider the patient's family history, medical history, and, of course, carefully examine phenotypic and visceral signs.

REFERENCES

1. Evert L. S., Borodun S. V., Bobrova E. I., Panicheva E. S., Kuznetsov V. S., Kachin S. V. Diagnosis of connective tissue dysplasia using biomarkers // Journal of SFU. Chemistry. 2009. No. 4.
2. 1. Nechaeva G. I., Yakovlev V. M., Konev V. P., Druk I. V., Morozov S. L. Connective tissue dysplasia: main clinical syndromes, diagnosis, treatment // Attending Physician. – 2008. – No. 2. – P. 22-25.
3. Zannad F, Pitt B. Biomarkers of extracellular matrix turnover // Heart Fail Clin. 2009. Vol. 5. No. 4. P. 589-99.
4. Saito M. Biochemical markers of bone turnover. New aspect. Bone collagen metabolism: new biological markers for estimation of bone quality // Clin Calcium. 2009. Vol. 19. No. 8. P. 1110-1117.

5. Ishikawa T, Sakuraba K. Biochemical markers of bone turnover. New aspect. Bone metabolism movement in various sports and physical activities // Clin Calcium. 2009. Vol.19. No. 8. P. 1125-1131.
6. Yakovlev V.M., Nechaeva G.I. Cardio-respiratory syndromes in connective tissue dysplasia. Omsk: OGMA, 1994. – 217 p.
7. Gromova O.A. Magnesium and pyridoxine: fundamentals of knowledge. – Moscow: ProtoTip, 2006. – 234 p.
8. Spasov A.A. Magnesium in medical practice. – Volgograd, 2000. – 272 p.
9. Senni K., Foucault-Bertaud A., Godeau G. Magnesium and connective tissue // Magnes Res. 2003. Vol. 16. No. 1. P. 70-74.
10. Dolgov V.V., Ermakova I.P. Laboratory diagnosis of mineral metabolism disorders and bone diseases: a textbook. – Moscow: RMAPO, 1998. – 64 p.
11. Laurant P., Hayoz D., Brunner H., Berthelot A. Dietary magnesium intake can affect mechanical properties of rat carotid artery // Br J Nutr. 2000. Vol. 84. No. 5. P. 757-764.
12. Leonard F., Moscovitz P., Hodge J.W., Adams J.P. Age-related Ca-Mg content and strength in turkey tendon // Calcif Tissue Res. 1976. Vol. 19. No. 4. P. 331-336.
13. Kadurina T.I., Gorbunova V.N. Connective tissue dysplasia. A guide for doctors. – St. Petersburg: Elbi-SPb, 2009. – 704 p.